
ANALYSIS OF DYNAMIC INTERACTION AMONG CLIMATE CHANGE, HUMAN HEALTH AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was undertaken to determine the dynamic relationship among climate change, human health and economic growth in Nigeria. The study made use of secondary data was sourced from different publications and data centres. Data on real gross Domestic Product, life expectancy, local carbon dioxide emissions, urbanization and food production were sourced from the World Development Indicators of the World Bank. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model. The study concluded that a dynamic relationship existed among climate change, human health and economic growth. The study recommends that for human health to improve economic growth in Nigeria, government should adopt measures to augment life expectancy in order to improve the health status of the Nigerian populace.

Keywords: Analysis, interaction, climate change, human health and Economic growth

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INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that Nigeria is a reflection of the sub-optimal economy with poor portable water, poor health care delivery and unhygienic environment (Okonjo-Iweala, 2004) is susceptible to the consequences of climate change which impede meaningful growth. Moreover, studies have shown that no meaningful developmental goals can be achieved as long as anthropogenic climate change is not controlled (McMichael, 2009 and Mawle, 2010). For instance, a country with high incidence and prevalence of disease has a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) that is five times lower than that of a country that does not have these negative incidences (Gallop and Sachs, 2001). According to Ajayi (2013), agriculture employs 70 per cent of Nigerian population, besides contributing about 41 per cent to Gross Domestic Product, in addition to accounting for 5 percent total export and 88 percent of non oil earnings. In spite of this huge contribution of agriculture to the economy, sustainability of and improvement on agricultural sector productivity have been difficult, as unpredictable weather patterns induce farm abandonment for non-farm activities, causing monumental reduction in food production which is vital for human health sustainability (Apata *et al.*, 2009). This suggests that unpredictable weather condition can also be inimical to vocational engagements and cause unproductive resource allocation across sectors in the economy. Consequently, all these upshots and resultant health challenges might even lead to deaths; thereby reducing the labour force and untimely lowering the general productivity of an economy. Therefore, to achieve any meaningful development goals in Nigeria, reducing the impact of climate change on human health is a crucial issue that the economy cannot afford to overlook. Accordingly, this study will examine the long-run effect of climate change on human health. In essence, if economic growth and development are to be stimulated, human health is a requisite condition (Haines *et al.*, 2016 and Dube and Chimbari, 2014). Prior medical and meteorological studies have explored the relationship between climate change and human health status; as well as made use of mostly descriptive statistics method of analysis (see Darwin and Tol, 2001; Kovats *et al.*, 2003; Van Liesshout *et al.*, 2004; Haines *et al.*, 2016; Eriksson, 2008; Nwoke *et al.*, 2009; Hutton, 2011). Also, there are studies on human health and economic growth (see Bloom *et al.*, 2004); Bloom and Canning, 2008; Peykarjou *et al.*, 2011; Ogungbennle *et al.*, 2013. Researchers have also investigated the relationship between climate change and economic growth (see Fankhauser and Tol, 2005; Dell *et al.*, 2008; Mendelsohn, 2009; Rahman *et al.*, 2009; Roson and Van der Mensbrugge, 2010). However, extent studies that have looked into the dynamic relationship among these tripartite – variables-climate change, human health and economic growth are not only sparse and inconclusive, but are also mostly cross-country analysis which might not account for their country specific peculiarities, especially for a country like Nigeria.

For instance, studies on Europe revealed that the old are more vulnerable to health hazard of climate change, contrariwise, in India, the impact of climate change was more extensive on children between the age of zero and fourteen years (Haines *et al.*, 2016; Mandal, 2008). Equally, some studies have it that the global effect of climate change is little while other studies argue otherwise (Mendelsohn, 2009; Eboli *et al.*, 2009; Roson and Van der Mensbrugge, 2010; Woodward *et al.*, 1998; Hardee and Mutunga, 2009). Thus, it becomes apropos to carry out a critical survey of the relationship among climate change, human health and economic growth in Nigeria. This is with a view to examining the link among the trio, besides assessing the consequences of the prevalent climate change on human health, including how the emissions of carbon dioxide vary climate conditions in Nigeria, and subsequently reduce the impact of climate change on human health in Nigeria, cum economic growth via improved economic policies.

Meanwhile, this study clearly departs from studies that adopted descriptive statistics or Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) economic model to predict changes in climate and its values, as Ackerman *et al.* (2001) made it clear that CGE models do not empirically achieve the expected result in environmental reviews, as they generate incorrect forecast. Moreover, the economic theory underlying CGE models is controversial and their techniques are defective for dynamic analysis. Hence, this study will add to knowledge by employing both descriptive and inferential statistics analyses; precisely, graphs and Vector Autoregressive (VAR) econometric technique which are most appropriate for dynamic analysis (Lutkepohl, 2005).

Research Questions

This study intends to answer the following pertinent questions:

- i. What is the profile of climate change, human health and economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the dynamic interaction among climate change, human health and economic growth in Nigeria?

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to empirically analyse the dynamic relationship among climate change, human health and economic growth in Nigeria.

Empirical Models

As earlier stated, this research study will specify its models by adopting the relevant variables expounded in the conceptual framework. It follows that anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions can cause climate change; climate change impairs human health both directly and indirectly and impaired human health in turn results in low productivity of labour and ultimately decline in economic growth. Poor health (poor physical and mental capabilities) reduces workers' productivity, as they both physically and mentally destabilised.

The health damage of climate change induced by air pollution causes economic loss (market impact) and also reduces people's happiness (non-market impact). The importance of the link from CO₂ to climate change; from climate change to human health and from human health to labour productivity and economic growth cannot overemphasised. Hence, we specify the different models below according to the conceptual framework specified.

Carbondioxide and Climate Change Variation

Carbondioxide is the primary greenhouse gas emitted through human activities and has been identified from the background to this study as the major cause of global warming which changes climate patterns, while variation in climate change is the deviation in long-term continuous changes in average condition of the climate. According to Hansen *et al.* (2011) the standard deviation of local surface temperature measures the typical magnitude of year-to-year variations of mean surface temperature. Hence, the study would have employed the standard deviation of the mean temperature in addressing this objective. However, Engle (2001) posited a preference for GARCH variance to correct for the deficiencies of least squares like assumption of homoscedasticity. Therefore, the data on variation in temperature will be generated from the mean surface temperature data using the standard tools of autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) and generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (GARCH).

The conceptual framework shows among others, two main variables of interest for this particular analysis: Carbondioxide and climate change variables, as literature has it that

CO₂ is a major compound that influences climate change because of its prevalence over other GHG and the decomposition of other GHG into CO₂ (McMichael, 2009 and Odjugo, 2010a). Thus, we will measure CO₂ and climate change variation with CO₂ emissions in kilo tonnes and GARCH variance temperature series, respectively.

Therefore, Equation 3.1.4 below is the empirical model for the second objective that accounts for the extent at which CO₂ emissions explain variation in climate change in Nigeria. This model makes use of both the global and the local CO₂ in explaining variation in climate change in Nigeria.

Drawing from the conceptual framework, the implicit form of the model is specified as;

$$LMTEMPV = f(LCO_2, GCO_2) \quad (3.1.1)$$

This equation states that *LMTEMPV* is a function of *LCO₂*, and *GCO₂*, which means the value of *LMTEMPV* is determined by the values of *LCO₂*, *GCO₂*.

Grossman and Krueger (1991) posited that growth leads to more air pollution at the initial stage which implies more CO₂ and more warming of the earth's surface temperature. Hence, we add RGDP to the equation above for the measurement of growth. Therefore, we assume that the economy is at the initial stage of growth. Hence, we have the model extended below:

$$LMTEMPV = f(LCO_2, GCO_2, RGDP) \quad (3.1.2)$$

Further empirical literature also establishes that there are negative correlations between rainfall and temperature (Cong and Brady, 2012); therefore, we add rainfall variable to our model and we have:

$$IMTEMPV = f(LCO_2, GCO_2, RGDP, LMRFALL) \quad (3.1.3)$$

The econometric representation of Equation 3.1.3 which is the main implicit model for the second objective of this study is specified thus:

$$LMTEMPV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LCO_2 + \beta_2 GCO_2 + \beta_3 RGDP + \beta_4 LMRFALL + u \quad (3.1.4)$$

Where;

LMTEPTV = Variation in local mean temperature

LCO₂ = Local carbondioxide emissions

GCO₂ = Global carbondioxide emissions.

RGDP = Real gross domestic product

LMRFALL = Local mean rainfall

u = Error term

A priori expectations: $\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 < 0$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research study has attempted to conceptualise the probable link among climate change, human health and economic growth in chapter three of this study. Therefore, given the unit root properties of RGDP, LEXP and GMTEMP/LMTEMP, we proceeded to determine whether there is a long-run co integration relationship among the series. Therefore, we equally used the Johansen full information maximum likelihood for this last objective.

The choice of Johansen multivariate cointegration technique as stated earlier is based on the fact that the variables for analysis are I(1) series and the model itself is multivariate.

Table 1

Johansen Cointegration Test for RGDP, LEXP and GMTEMP/LMTEMP

RGDP LEXP GMTEMP					
Trace			Maximum Eigen value		
Trace Statistic	5% Critical Value	<i>p</i> Values	Max-Eigen Statistic	5% Critical Value	<i>p</i> Values
60.00452	29.79707	0.0000**	54.22361	21.13162	0.0000**
5.780913	15.49471	0.7212	5.671835	14.26460	0.6556
0.109011	3.841466	0.7412	0.109077	3.841466	0.7412
RGDP LEXP LMTEMP					
Trace			Maximum Eigen value		
Trace Statistic	5% Critical Value	<i>p</i> Values	Max-Eigen Statistic	5% Critical Value	<i>p</i> Values
37.73253	29.79707	0.0050**	31.40164	21.13162	0.0013**
6.330896	15.49471	0.6564	6.181658	14.26460	0.5900
0.149238	3.841466	0.6993	0.142938	3.841466	0.6993
1 co integrating eqn detected			1 co integrating eqn detected		

Significance level: **=5%

The co integration result in the Table 5.11 showed that there is a co integrating long-run relationship between the RGDP, LEXP and GMTEMP/LMTEMP despite the non-stationery properties of variables employed. The presence of co integration between variables is consistent with the results found in other studies (McMichael, 2009; Ikefuji et al., 2012 and Ogungbennle et al., 2013). Thus, there is a probable dynamic relationship between climate change, human health and economic growth in Nigeria. Hence, we present the co integration equation from the Johansen co integration results reported in Tables 2

Table 2

Johansen Cointegration Equations for GMTEMP/LMTEMP, LEXP and RGDP

Equation for GMTEMP			Equation for LMTEMP		
RGDP	LEXP	GMTEMP	RGDP	LEXP	LMTEMP
1.000000	-15.75352	33.32145	1.000000	-5.253195	5.632949
	(1.26587)	(3.56921)		(0.38813)	(0.83716)
	[-12.4448]	[9.33580]		[-13.53463]	[6.77233]

() standard error; [] *t* statistic

These equations can be re-written as:

$$*RGDP = 15.753520*LEXP - 33.32145*GMTEMP + 38.32328$$

$$*RGDP = 5.2593195*LEXP - 5.632949*LMTEMP + 8.706888$$

As shown by the co integration equations above, which normalised the coefficients of RGDP both for the global and the local models, climate change and human health are significant in influencing changes in economic growth given the significant *t* statistics and the conforming signs to a priori explanation. The global climate change showed a greater negative impact on economic growth than the local climate change.

Vector Error Correction for Climate Change, Human Health and Economic Growth

The implication of co integration in I(1) series implies that VAR is not equally appropriate in tying the short-run disequilibrium of this models to their long-run values. Therefore, having tested for co integration and discovered a strong evidence of the same, we employed vector error correction mechanism (VECM) to capture both the long-run and short-run information on the dynamic relationship between the climate change, human health and economic growth. We determined the lag length from the values of AIC, BIC, and HQC selection criteria, bearing in mind that BIC is the most relevant for all sample sizes and annual time-series data.

Table 3

Lag Selection for Equations 3.3.7 and 3.3.8

Model with Global Mean Temperature (Eqn 3.3.7)			
Lags	AIC	SIC	HQC
0	-11.04549	-10.91487	-10.99944
1	-17.52683	-17.00437	-17.34264
2	-21.03828	-20.12397	-20.71594
3	-23.38540	-22.07925	-22.92492
4	-24.10102	-22.40303	-23.50240
5	-24.13997	-22.05013	-23.40320
Model with Local Mean Temperature (Eqn 3.3.8)			
Lags	AIC	SIC	HQC
0	-9.761638	-9.631023	-9.715590
1	-16.02091	-15.49845	-15.83672
2	-18.73306	-17.81876	-18.41073
3	-21.79862	-20.49247	-21.33814
4	-22.76970	-21.07179	-22.17117
5	-22.72474	-20.63490	-21.98797

Following Ivanov and Kilian (2005), we based our lag selection order on the result of SIC, as they posited that it is more accurate for all sample sizes. Having determined the lag order, we fitted a VEC regression analysis for both global and local climate change. Therefore, our original VAR model was converted into a VEC model, for both GMTEMP and LMTEMP. We bore in mind that we now have only one cointegrating equation. Hence, it takes the form below.

Where Θ is the parameter of the ECT and it measures the error correction mechanism that drives Y, back to its long-run equilibrium and Λ is the difference operator. Our variables are Y, X and T for RGDP, LEXP and GMTEMP/LMTEMP, respectively.

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